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Design of Annotated Bibliography of Traditional Medicine in West Java, Indonesia

Objective. The existence of traditional medicine, especially in the province of West Java, Indonesia, has been recognized and has been used by the general public, one of which concerns the traditional medicine. West Java is one of the largest provinces in Indonesia which has many medicinal plants. The purpose of this study is to create an information package that stores various sources of information related to traditional medicine in West Java by designing an annotated bibliography of traditional medicine in West Java. **Methods.** The research method used is action research method. The stages of action research used are planning, action, evaluation, reflection, and the process of publishing book products. **Results.** The results obtained are the stages of action in accordance with the stages of the plan for the annotated bibliographic manuscript to be printed as a book that can be tested by experts with a questionnaire containing suggestions. After being tested and corrected, the contents of the book were then tested publicly with a background in health sciences, information science, and libraries, as well as people who use traditional medicine in West Java by means of a questionnaire containing an assessment. **Conclusions.** The results of the public test are above 89%, which means the book product is feasible and can be published as an annotated bibliographic book related to traditional medicine.

Keywords: traditional medicine; medicinal plants; annotated bibliography of traditional medicine

Introduction

People in West Java Province, Indonesia, have known about and used traditional medicine for a long time. Based on data from the Central Bureau of Statistics, through the website <https://www.bps.go.id/>, it is known that the percentage of the male population in West Java in 2009 who used traditional medicine was 17.74%; in 2010, it was 22.75%; in 2011, 19.14%; in 2012 and 2013, it was 19.46%, and in 2014, it was 16.5%.

West Java is a province that has many medicinal plants, and this is in line with the statement from Roemantyo and Riswan (1990, as cited in Muwarni, 2015) that in West Java, Central Java, and East Java, there are known to be 151 types of plants used by the community as traditional medicine. Until now, the practice of traditional medicine has been recognized and considered legal because it has been regulated in Article 1 Paragraph 6 of Law no. 36 of 2009 concerning Health. In addition, one can refer to the Decree of the Minister of Health No. 659/Menkes/SK/X/1991 regarding how to make good traditional medicines, which regulates raw materials, technical responsibility, buildings where traditional medicines are made, equipment used to produce traditional medicines, sanitation, and hygiene, and processing and packaging.

Cholis (2012) states that of the 60% of people who use herbal medicine, 95% claim to benefit from traditional ingredients for health. In addition, he also stated that currently, 44 government hospitals include traditional medicine in their health services, although private hospitals do not. Ghosh (2011) stated that traditional medicine in terms of medicine is an essential aspect of traditional knowledge, which is indeed traditional medicine, including local knowledge based on experience for individuals in the community, then transmitted orally, becoming new information in the field of public health that is still being used today. With more people using traditional medicine, it is essential to have a place to store information from different sources. One

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of these sources is a book that gathers information from different places about traditional medicine in West Java. Where sources of information can be found from research results, printed books, ancient manuscripts, films, and recordings regarding traditional medicine in West Java, there are many of them. However, all of these sources of information have yet to be collected into one, so finding information is still challenging.

Never been an annotated bibliography of traditional medicine in West Java to make it easier to find information. All sources of information collected are combined into an annotated bibliography. A bibliography is a systematic list or enumeration of written works by a particular author or subject with one or more general characteristics (language, form, period, place of publication, etc.). The type of bibliography that the author chose, a descriptive bibliography, is shown in several forms of notes. This type of bibliography requires all the information needed to definitively identify certain documents.

A bibliography can be used as a guide to literature, saving time for people looking for information. It can also be used in the library field to introduce and promote specific libraries and find out how books, magazines, and recorded works have changed over time (Saleh, Nurwati, Tangkawarow, Bahri, & Wulandari, 2012; Lasa, 2009). Annotated bibliographies can be interpreted as a list of primary documents that usually consist of one or more subjects arranged systematically, followed by annotations or essays explaining the document's contents (Feranisa, Sukaesih, & Erwina, 2017). According to Kartadinata (2012), bibliographic annotations discuss a study from several interrelated sources. In addition, the description illustrates the reader's understanding of the collection source discussed.

The purpose of an annotated bibliography is to serve as reference material, with annotations that can assist researchers in evaluating whether the source is relevant to the topic (Reitz, 2004). By making this annotated bibliography of traditional medicine, it is hoped that the existence of traditional medicine will not only be in the form of utilization of natural resources through the actions of each individual, but also from a scientific point of view, one of which is through an annotated bibliography that can be used as reference material in further research or as a source of basic information on traditional medicine. The purpose of this study is to determine the possibility of creating an information package that stores various sources of information related to the folk medicine of West Java by developing an annotated bibliography of the folk medicine of West Java.

Methods

In the course of the study, scientists used action research methods. Coghlan and Brannick (2005) point out that action research is a democratic process that uses practical knowledge to find goals that will help people and the world. When creating an annotated bibliography as a book that could be used in the future as a source of health information according to Sulistio Basuki (1991), the researchers used the following stages: planning; activity, including data search using OPAC, as well as during the visits of university libraries, scientific research institutions, institutions of traditional medicine; assessment, including public testing; reflections.

Results and Discussion

The approach to designing an annotated bibliography uses the action research process cycle from Lee et al. (2019) with a modification for the researchers. The action research diagram is as follows:

Fig. 1. Action Research Cycle

(Source: Lee et al, 2019 with modification of the researchers)

The initial step begins with careful planning of what steps will be taken so that, when carrying out the research, nothing is left behind or forgotten with the desired end result. This stage is still a plan or initial activity design, the results of which are likely to change with ongoing research in the field. The plans carried out by the researchers include visiting various research institutions that have research on traditional medicine in West Java, visiting university libraries, and searching online using the OPAC facility of various institutional libraries and institutions on traditional medicine in West Java. Furthermore, the researchers determine the division of subject headings under 'traditional medicine' to facilitate the distribution of annotated bibliographical texts, determines the classification number of each subject heading, and determines how to make a good and correct annotated bibliographic index and bibliography. Then the researchers developed a concept for the content and appearance of the annotated bibliography so that it would not be monotonous and be able to invite readers to understand the contents of the book, and published an annotated bibliography in West Java as a published printed book.

After determining what plans will be carried out to design an annotated bibliography, the next step is to take various actions with different results as research in the field progresses. As for the several action steps of the researchers' plan, namely visiting research institutions, this was done to find out about annotated bibliographies and find sources of information as bibliographical data on traditional medicine in West Java. First, the researchers visited the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI-Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia) in Bandung, then the Center for the Preservation of Cultural Values (BPNB- Balai Pelestarian Nilai Budaya) in Bandung. After obtaining some data from research institutions, the next step was to visit the university library to check the availability of the data that had been found through the OPAC at the university. The universities visited were Universitas Padjadjaran and Universitas Indonesia.

The search for data is still continuing through the OPAC. First, the researchers collect fifty data from various sources with various types of data on one subject, namely traditional medicine in West Java. After that, verify the data, namely by first entering all data into Microsoft Excel to avoid data duplication and ensure that the data found discusses traditional medicine in West Java. As for the results of data verification, it was found that six of them were no longer collecting materials from the library of the relevant institution, because researchers found the data from search engines such as Indonesia OneSearch, Garuda Dikti, etc. As a result, the data was collected into 44 (forty-four) data sources of information whose existence can be found according to the locations listed. Data in the form of library materials is found more in terms of titles, which already describe the scope of the discussion in the West Java region. The library materials used are divided

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into several types, including research results such as theses, journals, and research reports, as well as articles or news articles. After finding the data, the next step is to divide the subject header and classification number. Based on the data that has been found, the subject headings are divided into two, namely 'Traditional Medicine' and 'Medicinal Plants', along with the division of subject headings in the annotated bibliography of traditional medicine in West Java:

1. Traditional Medicine
2. Traditional Medicine -- Traditional Medicine Practices
3. Medicinal Plants
4. Medicinal Plants – Ethnobotany
5. Medicinal Plants – Ethnopharmacology
6. Medicinal Plants – Ethnopharmacy

Because the subjects 'Traditional Medicine' and 'Medicinal Plants' were not in DDC 23, the researchers decided to find out what the classification number for the two subject headers was at the National Library of Indonesia. Through the book 'Subject Heading' written by Kuswosedjati, it is known that the subject 'Traditional Medicine' has a classification number of 615,882, while for 'Medicinal Plants' the classification number is 581,634.

Furthermore, for the manufacture of manuscripts, in accordance with the standards set by the National Library of Indonesia, the preparation of bibliographical manuscripts uses the National Library of Indonesia Main Catalog Application (KIN) to fill in all bibliographic data, which is then extracted into Microsoft Excel. All columns in Microsoft Excel will follow the columns in KIN. To make it easier to enter Mail Merger in Microsoft Word to create a bibliographical text, the sheets in Microsoft Excel are separated according to the discussion. The bibliographical manuscript is then created in Word Processor format using the Feature Mail Merge facility, in accordance with AACR2 guidelines. Then a title index is created that is divided into two according to the subject, namely for the subject headings 'Traditional Medicine' and 'Medicinal Plants'. Whereas the keyword index is the same as the 'title index', after mail merge it is arranged alphabetically, and the page numbers are listed according to the page numbers in the book.

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Aulana Yatias

Etnobotani tumbuhan obat di desa Neglasari, kecamatan Nyalindung, kabupaten Sukabumi, provinsi Jawa Barat / Aulana Yatias —Jakarta: Universitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah, 2014

85 halaman; 28 cm.

1. Tanaman obat -- Etnobotani

I. Judul

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui jenis-jenis tumbuhan obat, bagian tumbuhan yang digunakan oleh masyarakat desa Neglasari, kelompok penyakit yang diobati, dan cara pengolahannya. Dari penelitian ini dapat diketahui bahwa masyarakatnya memanfaatkan 64 jenis tumbuhan sebagai obat. Adapun tumbuhan yang paling banyak dimanfaatkan sebagai bahan obat tradisional oleh masyarakat didominasi oleh jenis tumbuhan dari famili Zingiberaceae. Tumbuhan obat terdiri dari 7 habitus yaitu perdu (20 jenis), pohon (14 jenis), herba (16 jenis), semak (7 jenis), tumbuhan memanjat (5 jenis), rumput (1 jenis), dan liana (1 jenis).

Kata kunci: Masyarakat desa, Sukabumi, Zingiberaceae

581.634

Billyardi Ramdhan

Keanekaragaman dan pemanfaatan tumbuhan obat asal kampung adat Cikondang, kabupaten Bandung, Jawa Barat / Billyardi Ramdhan —India: International Network for Natural Sciences, 2015

324 halaman ; 27 cm.

Fig. 2. Sample of Bibliography Page

At the evaluation stage, the researchers met with several experts (observation) to ask for an assessment of the book products that had been printed and asked for opinions and reviews from the experts to help the researchers correct the errors found in the book before the book was published or traded. An evaluation regarding the principles of annotated bibliography was carried out by one of the Unpad librarians and a scientific lecturer from the Biology department, FMIPA Unpad. The evaluation showed that the scientific names of the plants and fruits of the researchers were often wrong, so it also gave direction to the researchers to open links related to the scientific names of plants, namely theplantlist.org. After improving the contents of the book in accordance with the directions or revisions from experts, the next step is to distribute the book draft assessment questionnaire to the public, which represents the world of health in general and library science related to bibliographical manuscripts. The public test results were very good, with a percentage of ratings above 88% for ease of use and 90% for easy understanding of content, suitability of information, usefulness of bibliography, tidiness of bibliographical structure, as well as suitability and attractiveness of the cover and layout of the book.

The final stage is reflection. In order to improve the draft bibliographic book product, we should reflect on previous mistakes so that the research book product will be even better in the future. The plan's execution has changed, such as the use of the KIN application to create manuscripts, whereas the original plan only used Microsoft Excel as a database. In the action, the researchers use a list of subject headers as a search for classification numbers for each predetermined subject header, because the classification number for each subject heading is not found in DDC23. In addition, after completing the data verification stage, there are left forty-four

Biology lecturers. Furthermore, there was also a change in the cover because the image on the first book's cover was monotonous and did not attract attention.

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Розробка анотованої бібліографії традиційної медицини на Західній Яві, Індонезія

Мета. Традиційна медицина, особливо в провінції Західна Ява, Індонезія, була визнана та використовується широкою громадськістю. Західна Ява – одна з найбільших провінцій Індонезії, де росте

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безліч лікарських рослин. Метою даного дослідження є створення інформаційного ресурсу з традиційної медицини в Західній Яві шляхом розробки анотованої бібліографії. **Методика.** Використаний метод дослідження – метод дослідження дією. Використовувані етапи дослідження дії – планування, дія, оцінка, обмірковування, процес видання книжкової продукції. **Результати.** Отримані результати є етапами дій відповідно до етапів плану підготовки анотованого бібліографічного рукопису до друку у вигляді книги, яка може бути перевірена експертами за допомогою анкети з пропозиціями. Після тестування та виправлення зміст книги було публічно протестовано шляхом оцінного опитування за участю представників медичних наук, інформатики та бібліотек, а також людей, які використовують традиційну медицину в Західній Яві. **Висновки.** Результати публічного тестування перевищують 89 %; це означає, що книжковий продукт прийнятний і може бути виданий як анотована бібліографічна книга, пов'язана з традиційною медициною.

Ключові слова: традиційна медицина; лікарські рослини; анотована бібліографія традиційної медицини

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